

DUTIES AND ESSENCE OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF DEAF TEACHERS

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Abstract.

This article talks about the tasks, essence of the professional training of deaf teachers and the theory and practice of special education and training of children with hearing impairment "Special pedagogy".

Keywords: Special pedagogy, deaf pedagogy, UNESCO, brochure "Exemplary education"

Deaf pedagogy (derived from the Latin word "surdus" meaning "deafness") is a branch of defectology that deals with issues and problems of the education of people with hearing impairment. is a science. The main tasks of deaf pedagogy are pedagogically comprehensive study of hearing-impaired children, improvement of language teaching in a special school, development of hearing ability and promotion of pronunciation formation; to study and improve the laws of education of hearing impaired children, to increase the efficiency of the auditory perception development system, to get their graduates to work in a certain profession; improvement of technical means of teaching; ensuring the continuity of kindergarten and school education; It consists in coordinating the work of the medical and public education sectors in the republic, studying the problems of early diagnosis. Education of children with hearing impairment was carried out in a number of European countries.

The development of adult education is supported by UNESCO's International Commission on Education the main principles of lifelong learning, namely "learn to understand", "learn to do", "learn to live together". , the introduction of "learn to live" became the basis. In this, the need to change the educational policy and paradigm, the existing concept, aimed at creating new educational programs, new approaches to ensuring the quality of education, and introducing new forms of education is born. followed. Therefore, formal, informal and informal forms of education reflecting different levels of organization of educational services were introduced by UNESCO. Now it is necessary to pedagogically justify the use of didactic opportunities of formal, informal and informal education in the design of an individual education trajectory, professional development and professional development in lifelong learning. The development of adult education or continuous education in today's concept is related to the speed of the 21st century, the acquisition of information and communication technologies in all areas, and the consequences of changes in science, technology, and socio-economic relations as a result of digitization of education. One of the unique aspects of the adult education process is the conscious awareness that the system of acquired knowledge, skills and competencies is aimed at finding its place in the professional or life process, the clarity of the goal, the study-learning characterized by the strength of motivation. This requires a unique differential approach to the educational process, necessary pedagogical conditions and teaching technologies. Abu Nasr al-Farabi, in his treatise "Exemplary Education", specifically

focused on the issue of a good presentation of the material that learners should master, and one does not take too many things into account before gaining knowledge and experience. , after acquiring knowledge and gaining experience, he changes his view of things, he feels the necessity of things that he previously considered useless, what he did not pay attention to before now, on the contrary, amazes him.

The purpose of teaching the subject "Special pedagogy" (surd-pedagogy, oligophreno-pedagogy, typhlopedagogy) is to provide students of the faculty of defectology with knowledge and skills on the forms and methods of organizing the correctional education process in special institutions for children with mental and physical disabilities. and skills formation. "Special pedagogy" (surdo pedagogy) covers the theory and practice of the process of special education of hearing impaired children, the characteristics of hearing impaired children, their development, creation, application, and learning of correction tools. Students of the field of defectology of higher educational institutions get acquainted with the methodological foundations of special pedagogy, the current requirements of public education and pedagogy, the current state of the theory and practice of education and training of children with developmental disabilities. The science of "Special pedagogy" takes a leading place in this. The subject of "Special pedagogy" at the bachelor's degree of higher educational institutions includes the following:

theoretical knowledge of the basics of education and upbringing of children with developmental disabilities;

formation of practical professional skills;

development of pedagogical skills;

interest in the future profession, work on oneself and improve one's pedagogical skills.

According to their specialization, students get acquainted with the methodological foundations of deaf pedagogy, the current requirements of public education and pedagogy, the current state of the theory and practice of education and training of children with hearing impairment. In this regard, special attention is paid to the formation of practical skills in students, their acquisition of independent, critical thinking skills, professional knowledge and skills. In accordance with these requirements, not only theoretical materials are presented, but also a list of tasks is given for independent work of students. These tasks are different in terms of content. It includes tasks related to conscious perception of the material, distinguishing general and specific aspects of the reading process of hearing and hearing-impaired children, regrouping the material, and creating schemes and tables. It is envisaged that students will perform a number of tasks after attending a boarding school, during laboratory sessions or during pedagogical practice.

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